

Multi-Domain Transparent Service Provisioning in Multi-Band Optical Networks

Ramon Casellas¹, Enrique Fernández², Ricardo Martínez¹, Ricard Vilalta¹, Raül Muñoz¹, Antonio Buendía-López², Pablo Pavón-Marino^{2,3}

¹ CTTC-CERCA, Av. Carl Friedrich Gauss n7, 08860 Castelldefels, Barcelona, Spain

² E-lighthouse Network Solutions, Cartagena, Spain

³ Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena, Cartagena, Spain

e-mail: ramon.casellas@cttc.es, abuendia@e-lighthouse.com

ABSTRACT

Given the sustained traffic increase, transport optical networks need to evolve to provide additional capacity. While it is commonly admitted that long term solutions will rely on Spatial Domain Multiplexing (SDM) -- either by deploying bundles of standard single mode fibers or multi-core fibers --, short and mid-term solutions can achieve a more efficient usage of the fiber optical spectrum capacity by exploiting the different bands (beyond the C-band and even the already commercially available C+L systems). However, path computation in a multi-band environment becomes significantly more complex, critically due to physical layer impairment (PLI) effects such as Stimulated Raman Scattering (SRS). While this aspect has been explored in the context of single domain networks, the case of transparently connected multi-domain networks remains mostly unexplored, given the challenges associated to the trade-off between scalability and topology visibility/network abstraction.

In this paper, we present a proof-of-concept of a multi-domain media channel service provisioning transparently across emulated domains (optical line systems) leveraging the existence of multiple bands, using a hierarchical arrangement of controllers, where each domain relies on a dedicated OLS SDN controller. Such OLS controllers export a Transport-API (TAPI) North Bound Interface, extended to encompass PLI information about the supported optical bands. The parent orchestrator is responsible for path computation using abstracted information, and for orchestrating the provisioning by delegating segment control to the OLS controllers while ensuring a satisfactory QoT given the connection reach and physical layer impairment abstracted information. We evaluate aspects such as control plane latency and overall feasibility.

Keywords: Optical Network control, Multiband Networks, Multi-domain Networks, Network Orchestration

1. INTRODUCTION

A key enabler technology for evolving optical networks is multi band (MB) transmission, which offers increased capacity per fiber by exploiting the S-, E-, O- and U-bands in addition to C- and/or C+L-bands, maximizing the use of the currently deployed network infrastructure [1]. The diversity in performance characteristics across different frequency bands means that transmission can be flexibly adapted to the specific user needs, in introducing new challenges such as nonlinear effects (i.e. stimulated Raman scattering, SRS). This paper addresses the provisioning in multi-domain, multi-band optical networks. The application of Software Defined Networking (SDN) principles for the control of optical transport networks has been consolidated during the last years [2] to efficiently exploit the increasing programmability of network elements/devices. The purpose of this work is to demonstrate the application in a multi-domain, multi-band scenario. While the path computation is a critical aspect, the multiband model used in this work only addresses linear impairments but could be extended with specific tools such as GNPY [3] or ad-hoc models [4] which have proven useful in several scenarios by relying on generalized signal to noise ratio (GSNR) as an efficient QoT estimation.

2. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

2.1 Emulated Data Plane

The considered transparent network is multi-domain and includes two multi-band domains. Domains are interconnected by two inter-domain links, connecting ROADMs degree (line) ports belonging to the different domains. The purpose of this paper is to demonstrate control plane aspects. In this sense, the data plane is emulated. The considered devices are terminal devices -- which include tuneable, multi-band optical transceivers --, multiband ROADMs and in-line amplifiers (ILAs). Links connecting two devices and standard single mode fibers (SSMF), and are characterized by their type, attenuation (C-band 0,2 dB/Km, O-band 0,35 dB/Km) and distance. Amplifiers define their operating ranges, noise figure (5 dB NF C band, 6 dB NF O band) and configured gain. Finally, ROADMs can switch both bands (it is assumed a filter separates both bands, with per-band specific flexi-grid WSS are installed, covering the respective bands).

2.2 Control Plane for Partially disaggregated Networks with Externalized Path Computation

In this work, we consider a partial disaggregated scenario, where each transparent domain is controlled by a dedicated SDN controller (see Figure 1). Each domain has an optical line system controller that is responsible for: i) exporting a standard North Bound Interface (NBI) to the parent controller based on TAPI [5] including Physical Layer Impairments (Figure 2) and ii) provision the media channel (incl. the frequency slot) across the underlying infrastructure using SSMF links with C and O bands enabled.

Figure 1. Control Plane architecture for the multi-domain partially disaggregated scenarios.

2.2.1 Parent Orchestrator

The parent orchestrator with optional externalized path computation is responsible for: i) performing the RSA, including allocation of multi-domain oath and OTSi / frequency slot and corresponding media channel as well as the configuration of the transceivers. In the tested setup, it is based on the E-lighthouse Network Planner (ENP) software. The two OLS domain controllers first register in the parent controller. Then, the ENP is capable of performing the topology discovery on each of them, using the standardized TAPI access NBI exposed by the OLS controllers. The key topology discovery information retrieved is: i) the physical topology of the optical network, i.e. the multi-band ROADM and amplifier nodes, the line and client ports in them, and the fiber links (i.e. OTS, Optical Transmission System) and WDM sections on top of them (OMS, Optical Multiplexing Systems). It also retrieves the multiband media channel information in the links and ports, describing the two bands (O-band and C-band) available for transmission in our case. This also includes relevant information for optical impairments computation like amplifier noise figures and fiber attenuation coefficients, differently provided for O-band and C-band and ii) the provisioned optical paths. Each optical path basically represents a reserved bandwidth in a route inside each domain. The parent orchestrator is in charge of combining the information from the two domains, together with the information on the IP layer. This latter is retrieved from an inventory database also registered in the tool. This database contains information not present in the domains like: (i) inter-domain optical links, connecting a node in one domain with a node in the other, (ii) IP equipment in the network, composed of IPoWDM whiteboxes, equipped with 400G coherent optical pluggables, (iii) fiber connections between optical pluggables and the client-modules of the ROADMs.

3. MULTI-BAND MODELLING

3.1 Physical Layer Impairment Model

The Physical Layer impairment models is based on a simple multiband transmission modelling and accounts for OSNR estimation based on reach. The system accounts for amplifiers' noise factors (specific to C and O bands) and applies both to booster amplifiers as well as to in-line amplifiers) and fibers characteristics (attenuation, length and insertion losses).

3.2 Path Computation Function

The path and spectrum computation logic consists in: (i) produce the list of k-shortest paths between the end points to connect, (ii) for each of them, in order, find an available optical slot in the O-band using a modified first-fit approach, (iii) check the optical KPIs for that path/spectrum choice, and if they match the receiver tolerances, the path/spectrum is accepted. If no valid path/spectrum choice is found in the O-band, the process is repeated in the C-band. The rationale behind this is trying to use the O-band for shorter reach connections, since optical KPIs are out of margin in the longer ones, and as a by-product reserve the C-band for those longer connections. This is performed at the level of the parent orchestrator.

Figure 2. Multi-domain scenario composed of two domains with 4 ROADMs and 4 MB ILAs each, showing NBI extensions to characterize the photonic devices, as seen by both the OLS controllers.

4. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

Figure 3. [top-left] Orchestrator: multi-domain provision (purple) in C-band single-domain provision (green) in O-band. [top-right] Logs Multidomain Provision; [bottom] OTSI information about optical impairments.

The E-lighthouse Network Planner produces a unified multilayer IP and WDM view of the network, comprising all the aforementioned elements. This permits ENP to govern the provision of new IP connections between two pluggables in routers connected to the same or different domains. The sequence of actions for IP connection provision are: 1) determination of the optical path and allocatable spectrum between the two optical pluggables.

The heuristic first tries to find a valid path and spectrum in the O-band, and if not found repeat the attempt in the C-band. 2) if a valid path and spectrum was found, the orchestrator splits the route in the two domains (in multi-domain paths) and sends TAPI-based provisioning orders to the different OLS controllers in parallel, to appropriately reserve the sub-paths. Then, it configures the IP side of the provision in the IP routers. To illustrate this process, Figure 3 shows the ENP Graphical User Interface (GUI) plotting the IP and WDM network infrastructure, with the optical connections configured highlighted and a GUI screenshot with the optical impairments computed for two bidirectional optical connections (one in the O-band, one in the C-band).

4.1 Demonstrated Scenarios and Control Plane Latency

In this scenario, we provision first a service between 2 transceivers in the same domain. The allocated path uses the O-band since the a-posteriori QoT validation (in terms of OSNR, PMD, CD and power levels of the signal) is within the receptor tolerances and a second test is between 2 transceivers that are not in the same domain, and, in this case, the selected band is the C-band. For assessing the control plane latency values coming from the topology discovery, algorithm computation and provisioning phases, we provide in Table 1 averaged values coming from 10 repetitions of the tests. Note that: (i) discovery and provisioning phases are relatively fast, since they operate on an emulated hardware, (ii) path and spectrum computation benefit from an optimized implementation of the algorithms, and a simplified impairments calculation that does not consider in this setup the Raman scattering effects. Note that by having a parallelized behaviour of the requests, overall latency is minimized with regards to the serialized setup and values from ENP are affected by Internet latency.

	Measured at VPN / OLS (milliseconds)	Mean value ENP (milliseconds)
Discovery context	280 (empty) 492 (services)	931
Single-domain provision	2.5 (O-band)	309
Multi-domain provision	56 (C-band) parallel	515

Table 1. Measured latencies for context discovery and provisioning Times (left) and Figure 4. Wireshark capture of provisioning of a service from the ENP towards the OLS within a domain (right)

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has shown the provisioning of optical services across a multi-domain optical network. The transparent network exploits multiband as a short-term capacity increase. We have shown how, including the multidomain context, abstracted physical layer information is critical to perform efficient path computation. This relies on multiband transmission models that account for factors like per band attenuation or amplifier NF.

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